

OPTIMISATION OF THE PARAMETERS OF CYCLICAL-STREAMING TECHNOLOGY IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF KRYVBAS IRON ORE DEPOSITS

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ABSTRACT. The state of open-pit mining, formed at Ukrainian enterprises, as well as the state of the mineral raw materials market require the search for new, more economically feasible approaches to open pit mining operations. Such a solution is the widespread use of cyclical-streaming technology. The aim of the paper is to research the interconnection between the main technological parameters of cyclical-streaming technology.

In the paper relationships are established and the rational values of the parameters of the cyclical-streaming technology are determined, which contributes to improving the economic indicators of deposit development.

The mathematical modelling of the main parameters of the cyclical-streaming technology is fulfilled. The obtained results of studies of the main parameters of the cyclical-streaming technology can be used by project organisations and mining enterprises in the design.

The comparison of optimal indicators of operation of the excavator-automobile complex and cyclical-streaming technology is performed, as a result of which the economic expediency of the latter was confirmed. It has been established that increasing the carrying capacity of more than 136 tons at the current level of development of machinery and technology in iron ore open-pits in most cases is not appropriate. At the same time, the influence of the efficiency of the excavator unit on the performance of the cyclical-streaming technology in general was investigated. As a result, it was established that the best technical and economic indicators will be reached using the EKG-10 excavator. In this case, the geometric capacity of the dump truck body must correspond to the capacity of the bucket, and the load capacity is up to 130 tons. Thus, the study confirms the technological parameters of the cyclical-streaming technology that have been developed in the open-pits of the mining and processing plants of Kryvbas region.

Key words: the cyclical-streaming technology, excavator-automobile complex, equipment performance

The problem and its connection with scientific and practical tasks

Further development of opencast mining will be characterised by a gradual deterioration of mining conditions of deposit development. At the same time, the current state of Kryvbas open pits is characterised by their considerable depth and their further growth to the design marks. However, the increase in depth is accompanied by an increase in the volume of overburden, that is removed from the open-pit and this increases the load on the system of transportation of rock mass. Mining conditions for the development of mineral deposits in the coming years will be characterised by a further increase in the depth of open-pits and transportation distances, increasing the part of strong rocks and ores in total rock mass, as well as the need for selective development and averaging of ores while concentrating on lower horizons and in cramped conditions.

All this requires the use of several, mostly combined, modes of transport in the development of deposits, in combination with the existing quarry excavating equipment – cyclical-streaming technology (CST). If in the past the question of application of CST was raised, today's mining and technical-economic conditions demand search and the reasonable choice of the most rational parameters of cyclical-streaming technology, especially: working parameters and standard size of the excavating equipment, automobile and conveyor transport, parameters of elements of the development system, etc.

Analysis of research and publications

In recent years, the depth of the iron ore open-pits of Krivbas («Central MPP», «Pivnichniy MPP», «Inguletskiy MPP», «AMKR») has been increased by 100-150 m and is currently 300-450 m. For example, the depth of «Arcelor Mittal Kriviy Rih» open-pit № 2b is 300 m, open-pit №3 is 375 m,

«Inguletskiy MPP» is 450 m, «Central MPP», open-pit №1 is 400 m, open-pit №3 is 315 m, «Pivnichniy MPP» Gannivskiy open-pit is 350 m). In the future, in accordance with the completed technical projects, the development depth will increase to 500-700 m (Chetverik et al., 2010, 2012, 2014; Bass, 2017). At such depths, the problems of rock mass transportation due to excessively long transportation distances become even more complicated. Currently, the widespread is the use of road delivery of rocks and minerals by heavy-duty dump trucks, the flexibility of which is still its main advantage over other modes of transportation. However, the constant increase in the cost of diesel fuel, tyres, lubricants, which account for up to 90% of operating costs for road delivery of rock mass necessitates the use of a more economical method of transporting minerals and rocks to the surface – a conveyor in combination with road transport in a quarry, i.e. CST.

The feasibility of using CST is justified primarily by a significant reduction in operating costs compared to variants that involve the use of an open-pit road or rail transport. Thus, according to foreign practice, the use of crushing complexes in the open-pit and conveyor transport significantly reduces operating costs compared to the transportation of ore by dump trucks. This creates favourable conditions for more efficient mining and reducing the amount of exhaust gases. However, one of the disadvantages of the applied CST schemes is the permanent position of crushing and conveyor complexes, the use of which does not correspond to the dynamics of mining operations and the conditions of formation of technological cargo flows.

Although CST is cheaper than road transport, with increasing depth of open-pits, its use with a stationary crushing and reloading points becomes less profitable.

According to (Yakovlev, 2003; Rakishev, 2012), the permanent position of crushing and conveyor complexes

facilities and the irrationality of the mining schemes used in such cases result in a large amount of mining capital and installation works (up to 75% of the total cost of the complexes).

The placement of crushing and reloading points require a large working berm of significant size, for which it is necessary to perform additional volumes of excavation work (from 2 million m³ for a depth of 100 m to 10 million m³ of rock mass at a depth of 500 m).

Large volumes of mining and capital works result in longer construction times of crushing and conveyor complexes which take, as a rule, not less than 3-5 years (Karmayev, 2012; Trubetskoy et al. 2015).

The development of a scientific basis of the cyclical-streaming technology can be divided into several stages (Reshetnyak, 2015).

Depending on the size of the open-pit, the use of the CST complex at the first stage allows to reduce the volume of current overburden to an average of 5 million m³. At the same time at CPT with a steeply inclined conveyor the volumes of mining and capital works decrease 3-4.5 times, expenses of diesel fuel are reduced 1.8-2.5 times, dust emission and emissions of toxic components in the atmosphere decrease by 35-45%.

The next stage in the development of a cyclical-streaming technology was the creation and implementation in the open-pits of mobile crushing and reloading points, equipped with steeply inclined conveyors designed to lift the rock mass to higher benches (Shemetov, 2007). The structure of such a complex includes a hopper, feeder, crusher and a steeply inclined belt conveyor (type "sandwich") with a clamping belt. Another feature of this crushing and reloading point is the installation of a compact and high-performance auger crusher instead of the traditional jaw or conical one. The use of such a loader with a capacity of 2000 m³/h at the Muruntau open-pit (Uzbekistan) allowed to reduce the distance of rock mass transportation by road by 480 m and the lifting height by 60 m (Yakovlev, 2003).

According to Muruntau open-pit experts (Kucherskiy et al., 2005), the advantages of CST based on steeply inclined conveyors are not only the reduction in the cost of transportation of rock mass, but also the significant reduction in preparatory work because the conveyors can be placed on a narrow strip of the reconstructed section of the open-pit board practically without additional capital trenches and penetration of inclined trunks. However, as the analysis shows, at this time the part of rock mass removed from open-pits by CST in the CIS countries is still very small (only 10-15%), while in the enterprises of Canada, USA, Chile, Australia, it exceeds 50% of total mineral production (Chetverik et al., 2010). Therefore, in order to significantly improve the economic performance of large mining companies, as well as to reduce the negative impact of mining on the environment, it is advisable to significantly expand the use of cyclical-streaming technology in these enterprises.

Formulation of the problem

Based on the analysis of scientific advances on the use of cyclical-streaming technology in the open-cast development of deposits, there is a need to establish mathematical dependences and rational values of the parameters of CST.

Presentation of material and results

The main link, the crushing and conveyor complex (CCC), through which the supply of ore to the CCC is stopped, is characterised by the following downtimes. The duration of maintenance and scheduled repairs of equipment, carried out in accordance with the standards for repair schedules, reaches 7.5 – 10.5% of the calendar time. Downtime of the complex for technological and organisational reasons with the number of stops of up to 80 – 140 is 35 – 74 hours per month. Due to emergency reasons, CCC stand for 48 – 78 hours with the number of stops 90 – 140 during the month. It follows that each complex during the year stops about 1000 – 1680 times, briefly changing the state of the transport system due to a decrease in its productivity at such intervals. The average decrease in system productivity due to stops of the crushing-conveyor complex in some months is 4.6 - 6.2%. However, it is obvious that most of the downtime of the crushing complex is due to emergency stops as a result of equipment failure. The solution to this issue is beyond the scope of this research.

Irregular operation of gathering vehicles leads to a decrease in the productivity of the crushing and conveyor complex and excavator unit. The overall decrease in the average variable productivity of the CST system due to the lack of dump trucks in some months varies in the range of 1.6 - 3.7%. For the crushing and conveyor complex and excavator link, this indicator is 0.2 - 2.3% and 0.8 - 1.8%, respectively. In certain periods of time to perform the planned tasks, crushing and conveyor systems are serviced by dump trucks, which quantitatively exceed the number required to ensure average hourly productivity. This reserve of gathering equipment, as usually, is suboptimal and practically does not give the required increase in hourly cargo flow. Such measures increase the overall unevenness of cargo flows, violating the modes of excavation of other types of rock mass in the open-pit.

For example, due to the fact that for the maintenance of the crushing and conveyor complex "hor. - 195 m" in the Pershotravneviy open-pit of «Pivnichniy MPP» in one of the years of its stable operation were spent 10% more track-hours than the required level, the volume of removal of overburden from the open-pit decreased by 7%.

Thus, one of the main parameters of the CST is the production capacity of the transport link. To study this question, we turn to the paper of Suprun and co-authors (2014). Figure 1 shows the results of research conducted by "Caterpillar" and "Komatsu" on behalf of JSC "Chernihivets", namely the dependence of the cost of removal of 1 tkm on the load capacity of the dump truck.

It is obvious that with increasing the load capacity, the transportation costs decrease. However, the intensive reduction occurs only in zone A (Figure 1) with an increase in load capacity from 40 to 130 tons, and further reduction is quite insignificant. But the carrying capacity of dump trucks used in domestic open-pits has already reached zone B of this schedule, so its further increase is impractical without good technological reasons.

According to Table 1, the internal shifts of a simple excavator unit for technological and organisational reasons reached 825 hours per month.

Fig. 1. Dependence of the cost of removal of 1 tkm on the carrying capacity of the dump truck («Caterpillar» & «Komatsu»)

The number of excavators that serve crushing and conveyor systems varies in a wide range of 8 - 15 machines per shift. At the same time, for about 75% of the shifts, the crushing and conveyor complexes are serviced by 10-12 excavators. Most often, excavators are involved in ancillary work (disassembly of

faces, cleaning oversized pieces of rock mass, cleaning of faces and horizons), busy by moving to a new place of work or from the blasting zone or stand idle due to lack of dump trucks.

Downtime of excavators due to equipment failures is 2-2.5 times less than the downtime for technological and organisational reasons. The average decrease in productivity of CST complexes due to downtime of excavators during different months varies between 8.7 -14.7%, which is about 50 - 65% of the total average decrease in productivity of the system of cyclical-streaming technology.

Therefore, to investigate the interdependence of excavator bucket capacity, excavator productivity and utilisation ratio on the efficiency of the system of cyclical-streaming technology.

To do this, we calculate the productivity of excavators EKG-4.6, EKG-5, EKG-8I, EKG-10, EKG-12.5, EKG-15 and EKG-20 for different utilisation ratios and for each value set the specific costs. The results of such calculations for the utilisation ratio $k_v = 0.55$ are given in Table. 2.

Similarly, the values of the reduced costs were obtained for $k_v=0.6$, $k_v=0.65$, $k_v=0.7$ (Table 3).

According to the obtained data for $k_v=0.55$, $k_v=0.6$, $k_v=0.65$, $k_v=0.7$, the dependences of the reduced costs on the productivity of excavators were constructed, they are shown in Figure 2.

Table 1. Reduction of production capacity of the complex of cyclical-streaming technology due to technological downtime of adjacent units

Technological link of the CST system	The share of reduction of average variable production capacity by months											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Excavator	0.51	0.50	0.59	0.54	0.57	0.59	0.54	0.55	0.51	0.51	0.57	0.65
Road gathering	0.1	0.15	0.15	0.11	0.12	0.11	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.09
Crushing and conveyor complexes	0.33	0.31	0.28	0.26	0.25	0.24	0.28	0.30	0.33	0.30	0.29	0.22
Crushing and concentrating factory	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.09	0.06	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.07	0.11	0.05	0.04

Table 2. Calculation of excavator productivity and reduced costs for $k_v=0.55$

Excavator	Bucket capacity, m ³	k_v	Productivity, m ³ /year	CAPEX, c.un./year	OPEX, c.un./year	Reduced costs, c.un./year
EKG -4.6	4.6	0.55	1785818.57	74883.31	1499142.9	1510375
EKG -5	5	0.55	1863462.86	79630.057	1500487.1	1512432
EKG -8I	8	0.55	2329328.57	112598.83	3106003.9	3122894
EKG -10	10	0.55	2451924.81	132729.13	4767003.1	4786912
EKG -12.5	12.5	0.55	2773010.2	156458.3	5956079.6	5979548
EKG -15	15	0.55	2911660.71	178962.94	7440398.6	7467243
EKG -20	20	0.55	3583582.42	221235.82	9521495.3	9554681

Fig. 2. Dependencies of the reduced costs on productivity of excavators for kv=0.55, kv=0.6, kv=0.65, kv=0.7

The graph shows that with increasing the productivity, the costs are reduced. But at the same time, the lowest costs are

characteristic of larger values of the utilisation factor. Therefore, when substantiating the productivity of the excavator link, it is necessary to take into account the conditions of use of loading and unloading equipment, as well as the current state of transport communications, which determine the possibility of using more powerful transport equipment.

However, these calculations are theoretical. In fact, based on the experience of MPP, higher utilisation ratio is typical for excavators of smaller sizes. Therefore, in Table 4 the dependences of the reduced costs on the productivity of excavators during their operation with the corresponding empirical coefficients of equipment use are summarised, and in Figure 3 these data are visualised by the range of values and given a correlation line that can be described by the equation $y = 6 \cdot 10^7 x^2 + 3.6665x - 10^7$. The correlation ratio was $R^2=0.8455$.

Table 3. Calculation of excavator productivity and reduced costs for kv=0.6, kv=0.65, ma kv=0.,7

Excavator	Productivity. m ³ / year / Reduced costs. c.un./year		
	kv =0.6	kv =0.65	kv =0.7
EKG -4.6	1948165.714 / 1646661	2110512.86 / 1782947	2272860 / 1919233
EKG -5	2032868.571 / 1648839	2202274.29 / 1785247	2371680 / 1921655
EKG -8I	2541085.714 / 3405258	2752842.86 / 3687622	2964600 / 3969986
EKG -10	2674827.068 / 5220276	2897729.32 / 5653640	3120631.58 / 6087004
EKG -12.5	3025102.041 / 6521010	3277193.88 / 7062472	3529285.71 / 7603934
EKG -15	3176357.143 / 8143643	3441053.57 / 8820043	3705750 / 9496443
EKG -20	3909362.637 / 10420271	4235142.86 / 11285862	4560923.08 / 12151452

Table 4. Calculation of excavator productivity and reduced costs for empirical values kv

Excavator	kv	Productivity, m ³ /year	CAPEX, c.un./year	OPEX, c.un./year	Reduced costs, c.un./year
EKG -4.6	0.8	2597554.286	74883.3102	2180571.498	2191803.995
EKG -5	0.78	2642729.143	79630.05698	2127963.485	2139907.993
EKG -8I	0.75	3176357.143	112598.8269	4235459.8	4252349.624
EKG -10	0.7	3120631.579	132729.1265	6067094.809	6087004.178
EKG -12.5	0.65	3277193.878	156458.2999	7039003.184	7062471.929
EKG -15	0.6	3176357.143	178962.939	8116798.43	8143642.871
EKG -20	0.55	3583582.418	221235.8209	9521495.279	9554680.652

At the same time the larger number of smaller excavators promote more equitable development of mining operations on the ledges and reduce process downtime.

Fig. 3. Dependence of the reduced expenses on productivity of excavators for empirical values k_v

Table 4 shows that with increasing the size of the excavators, the utilisation ratio of the equipment decreases over time (in each case, a dump truck with a capacity of 130 tons is used). This is explained by the fact that for the use of more powerful dump trucks it is necessary to increase the width of the road and, accordingly, the width of the working area, which will reduce the angle of the working board and, accordingly, worsen the mining regime.

At the same time, the capacity of the excavator bucket should correspond to the load capacity of the dump truck, which, in turn, is recommended to be within 130 tons. Today, with the current level of development of equipment and technology, such a combination will provide the highest technical and economic performance of open-cast mining. At the same time, the experience of domestic iron ore open-pits confirms the research data.

Conclusions and directions of further research

The paper discusses in detail the interconnection between the parameters of CST. The reduced costs of transportation, the number of dump trucks and the productivity of the excavator-automobile complex in the CST and their dependence on the depth of deposit development are analysed. Particular attention is paid to the comparison of the optimal productivity of the excavator-automotive complex and cyclical-streaming technology, which confirms the economic feasibility of the last one. It is found that increasing the carrying capacity to more than 136 tons at the current level of development of machinery and technology in iron ore open-pits in most cases is not appropriate. At the same time, the influence of the efficiency of the excavator link on the productivity of the CST as a whole is investigated according to the criterion of minimum equipment downtime.

As a result, considering the current state of open-cast mining it is found that for the conditions of iron ore open-pits of Kryvbas the best technical and economic indicators will be achieved when using excavators with a bucket capacity of 10 - 12.5 m³. Thus, the research confirms the technological parameters of

cyclical-streaming technology that have been developed in the open-pits of mining and processing plants.

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